

SILINDRIK SIMMETRIYALI PORTLASH PAYTIDA ZARBA TO'LQINI FRONTIDAGI BOSIM VA TO'LQIN RADIUSINING O'ZGARISHI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada to'lqin radiusi frontidagi bosimning to'lqin radiusiga bog'liqligi ko'rib chiqiladi, bu butun bo'shliqni egallagan bir jinsli gruntidagi zaryadning portlashi natijasida yuzaga keladi, ya'ni chegara yuzalarini hisobga olmagan holda. Zarba to'lqini oldidagi kuchlanish, odatda ε^* va ε_i^* ga bog'liq bo'lgan funktsiya sifatida aniqlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Grunt, silindrik simmetriya, portlash, plastik gaz, bosim, to'lqin radiusi, yuqori kuchlanish, zarba to'lqini.

Abstract: The article examines the dependence of the pressure on the wave radius front on the wave radius, which occurs as a result of the explosion of a charge on a homogeneous ground occupying the entire space, that is, without considering the boundary surfaces. The voltage in front of the shock wave is usually defined as a function of ε^* and ε_i^* .

Key words: Grunt, cylindrical symmetry, explosion, plastic gas, pressure, wave radius, high voltage, shock wave.

Gruntida radiusi r_0 bo'lgan silindrsimon zaryad portlaganda, bir lahzada, hajmini o'zgartirmasdan, zaryad yuqori bosimli gazga aylanadi, deb taxmin qilinadi. Bu gaz politropik qonunga muvofiq γ politrop indeksi bilan kengayadi. Olingan yuqori bosim zarba to'lqinining shakllanishi bilan butun atrof-muhitga tarqaladi, deb taxmin qilinadi.

Grunt plastik gaz sifatida qaraladi [1]. Binobarin, qo'yilgan yuklama olinish vaqtida zarracha tomonidan oldin olingan zichlik o'zgarmaydi.

Masalaga mexanik va matematik nuqtai nazardan yondashib, normal va urinma kuchlanishlarning birgalikdagi ta'sirini hisobga olgan holda, ularning invariantligini hisobga olib, Lagranj o'zgaruvchilarida gruntning bir o'lchovli dinamik harakati uchun biz tomonimizdan tenglama chiqarilgan [4,6]:

$$\rho_0 r \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = (r+u) \frac{\partial \sigma_r}{\partial r} + (\sigma_r - \sigma_\varphi) \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r+u) + \frac{\partial \tau_\varphi}{\partial \varphi} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r+u) \quad (1)$$

bu yerda, r - zarrachaning tinch holatdagi koordinata boshigacha bo'lgan masofasi.

Bunday holda, tuproq uzluksizligining Lagranj o'zgaruvchilaridagi tenglamasi va bog'liqlik gruntlarning fazoviy harakati holatida Mizes-Shleyxer-Botkin plastik sharti quyidagi ko'rinishlarga ega bo'ladi [5]:

$$\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r+u)^2 = \frac{\rho_0}{\rho} r, \quad \sigma_r - \sigma_\varphi = -\frac{\tau_0}{1+2\mu} + \frac{3\mu}{1+2\mu} \sigma_r \quad (2)$$

τ_0 va μ koeffitsientlar har tomonlama sof "kuchlanish" ga eng yuqori qarshilik H_0 va gruntning oktaedral maydondagi ichki ishqalanish burchagi ψ bilan ushbu munosabatlar orqali bog'langan

$$\tau_0 = \sqrt{3} H_0 \operatorname{tg} \psi, \quad \mu = \frac{\operatorname{tg} \psi}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (a)$$

(1) va (2) tenglamalar tizimi quyidagi to'rtta noma'lum funktsiyalarni o'z ichiga oladi: asosiy kuchlanishlar σ_r va σ_φ ; siljish u va zichlig ρ va shuning uchun ochiq tizimni tashkil qiladi.

Tenglamalar tizimini yopish uchun yuqori kuchlanishlarda gruntning mexanik xususiyatlarini $\sigma(\varepsilon)$ va $\sigma_i(\varepsilon, \varepsilon_i)$ ko'rinishda aniqlash bo'yicha mualliflar tomonidan o'tkazilgan eksperimental tadqiqotlar natijalaridan foydalanilgan [2, 3]; gruntedan yuklamani olganda $\sigma(\varepsilon)$ bog'liqlik yoki $\rho = \text{const}$ shart bilan, yoki $\sigma(\varepsilon) = \phi(\varepsilon, \varepsilon_{\max})$ bog'liqlik bilan almashtiriladi ($\varepsilon_{\max}$ - tuproq massivlari zarrasining maksimal hajmli deformatsiyasi).

Grunt va tog' jinslarining asosiy mexanik xossalari quyidagi invariant munosabatlar ko'rinishida keltirilgan:

a) o'rtacha normal kuchlanish va hajmli siqish deformatsiyasi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik fizik chiziqli bo'lmagan funktsiya bo'lib, u eksperimental natijalar sifatida, masalan, quyidagi shaklda approksimatsiy qilinadi

$$F(\varepsilon) = k_1 \varepsilon + k_2 \varepsilon^2 + k_3 \varepsilon^3 \quad (3)$$

b) kuchlanish intensivligi va siljish deformatsiyalarining intensivligi ε_i o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik, tajriba natijalari sifatida quyidagi ko'rinishdagi kasr-chiziqli (giperbolik) funktsiya bilan approksimatsiy qilingan

$$\frac{\sigma_i(\varepsilon, \varepsilon_i)}{H_0 + F(\varepsilon)} = \frac{G_0 \operatorname{tg} \psi}{\operatorname{tg} \psi + G_0 \varepsilon_i} \varepsilon_i$$

bo'lib, bu elastik potentsial $U(\varepsilon, \varepsilon_i)$ mavjudligi haqidagi gipotezaga mos keladi. Bu yerda, $k_1, k_2, k_3, H_0, \operatorname{tg} \psi, G_0$ - muallif tomonidan tajribalar natijasida olingan o'zgarmaslar [4].

Zarba to'liqini oldidagi kuchlanish, odatda ε^* va ε_i^* ga bog'liq bo'lgan funktsiya sifatida aniqlanadi [6]:

$$-\sigma_r^* = \frac{\rho_0}{1-b(r^*)} \frac{(R\dot{R})^2}{r^{*2}} + \left[\frac{\sigma(\varepsilon^*)}{\varepsilon^*} + \frac{4}{9} \frac{\sigma_i(\varepsilon^*, \varepsilon_i^*)}{\varepsilon_i^*} \right] \varepsilon^* + p_\alpha \quad (4)$$

[6] dagi ilmiy maqolada isbotlanganiga ko'ra, algebraik o'zgartirishlar va almashtirishlardan so'ng (1) tenglama y ga nisbatan R (vaqtning ixtiyoriy momentidagi o'choq radiusi) argumentli birinchi tartibli tenglamaga keltiriladi:

$$y' + F(R)y = Q(R) \quad (5)$$

uning yechimi quyidagi ifoda bilan beriladi

$$y = e^{-\int_{r_0}^R F(R) dR} \left\{ y_0 + \int_{r_0}^R Q(R) e^{\int_{r_0}^R F(R) dR} dR \right\}$$

bu yerda,

$$F(R) = 2 \left\{ \left[(m(R))^{\frac{\nu}{2}} - 1 \right] - \frac{\nu}{\nu-2} \left[(m(R))^{\frac{\nu}{2}} - 1 \right] + \frac{\nu b_1}{1-b_1} (m(R))^{\frac{\nu}{2}-1} \right\} \cdot \left\{ R(m(R))^{\frac{\nu}{2}} - 1 \right\}^{-1}, \nu = \frac{6\mu}{1+2\mu}$$

$$Q(R) = \left\{ \frac{2\nu b_1}{\rho_0} \left(\frac{r_0}{R} \right)^{2\nu} p_0 - \frac{2\nu b_1}{\rho_0} (m(R))^{\frac{\nu}{2}} p_\alpha - \frac{4\nu_0 b_1}{\rho_0(1+2\mu)} \left[(m(R))^{\frac{\nu}{2}} - 1 \right] + \right. \\ \left. + \frac{2\nu b_1}{\rho_0} (m(R))^{\frac{\nu}{2}} \left[\frac{\sigma(\varepsilon^*)}{\varepsilon^*} + \frac{4}{9} \frac{\sigma_i(\varepsilon^*, \varepsilon_i^*)}{\varepsilon_i^*} \right] \varepsilon^* \right\} \cdot \left\{ R(m(R))^{\frac{\nu}{2}} - 1 \right\}^{-1}, m(R) = \frac{R^2 - b_1 r_0^2}{(1-b_1)R^2}$$

$t = 0, R = r^* = r_0$ bo'lganda zarracha tezligining boshlang'ich qiymati:

$$y_0 = \frac{1-b_1}{\rho_0} \left\{ p_0 - p_\alpha - \left[\frac{\sigma(\varepsilon^*)}{\varepsilon^*} + \frac{4}{9} \frac{\sigma_i(\varepsilon^*, \varepsilon_i^*)}{\varepsilon_i^*} \right] \varepsilon^* \right\}$$

Endi silindrik simmetriyali portlash paytida ko'p qatlamli muhitning kuchlanish-deformatsiya holatining sonli tahlilini o'tkazamiz. Bu yerda namligi 11% bo'lgan qumloq muhit qaralgan. Uning $2200 \frac{kg}{sm^2}$ gacha bo'lgan dinamik egri chizig'i quyidagi formula bilan approksimatsiya qilingan

$$\frac{p - p_H}{p_\alpha} = 2518 \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} - 1 \right) - 13970 \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} - 1 \right)^2 + 60370 \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} - 1 \right)^3 \quad (6)$$

bu yerda - $p_H = 2 \frac{kg}{sm^2}, p_\alpha = 1 \frac{kg}{sm^2}, \rho_0 = 168,71 \cdot 10^{-4} \frac{kg \cdot sek^2}{sm^2}$.

$p = 2200 \frac{kg}{sm^2}$ bo'lganda (6) formula yordamida hisoblanadi. Yopishqoqlik

koefitsienti va ichki ishqalanish burchagi quyidagi qiymatlarga ega:

$k = 0,5 \frac{kg}{sm^2}, \psi = 73^\circ$. Ushbu qiymatlar yuqorida kiritilgan parametrlarni aniqlash

uchun ishlatiladi: $\mu = 0,167, \nu = 0,751, \tau_0 = 192,68 \frac{kg}{sm^2}$.

Boshlang'ich momentda zaryadning radiusi, gazning bosimi (portlash mahsuloti) va politropik indeks quyidagi qiymatlarga ega edi:

$$r_0 = 30sm, p_0 = 14 \times 10^4 \frac{kg}{sm^2}, \gamma = 1,5.$$

(5) tenglamani sonli yechish uchun Mathcad dasturi yordamida Runge-Kutta usulidan foydalanilgan va hisoblash natijalari rasmlarda ko'rsatilgan.

1-rasm. zarba to'liqini frontidagi bosimning to'liqin radiusiga nisbatan o'zgarishi (zarba to'liqini frontida $\sigma_r^*(\varepsilon, \varepsilon_i)$ bog'lanish hisobga olingan)

2-rasm. zarba to'qlini frontidagi bosimning to'qlin radiusiga nisbatan o'zgarishi (zarba to'qlini frontida $\sigma_r^*(\epsilon, \epsilon_i)$ bog'lanish hisobga olinmagan)

1 va 2-rasmlarda zarba to'qlini bosimi P^* ning zarba to'qlini fronti r^* ga bog'liqligi keltirilgan. Kuchlanishlar orasidagi bog'lanishni hisobga olmagan bosim - $P(r^*)$ va hisobga olgan holda bosim - $P^*(r^*)$ deb belgilangan.

Jarayon boshida r^* (30;31,7) oraliqda o'zgarganda $P(r^*)$ ning qiymati $P^*(r^*)$ qiymatiga nisbatan kichik, (31,7;40,9) oraliqida katta, (40,9;53,8) oraliqda kichik, (53,8;90) oraliqda esa deyarli bir xil, almashinib keladi. Shundan so'ng, 0,9 metrdan 137,5 metrgacha, ya'ni zarba to'qlinining intensivligi to'xtaguncha $P(r^*)$ ning qiymati $P^*(r^*)$ qiymatidan kichik bo'lib, $r^* = 1,348$ metrdagi bu farq eng yuqori bosim $1945 \cdot 10^4 \frac{kg}{m^2}$ ga to'g'ri keladi, eng past bosim esa $r^* = 120,9$ metrda

$2,74 \cdot 10^4 \frac{kg}{m^2}$ ga teng.

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